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FarpScusn: Fully Anonymous Routing Protocol with Self-healing Capability in Unstable Sensor Networks

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Abstract: Anonymous technology is an effective way to protect users' privacy. Anonymity in sensor networks is to prevent the unauthorized third party from revealing the identities of the communication parties. While in unstable wireless sensor networks, frequent topology changes often lead to route-failure in anonymous communication. To deal with the problems of anonymous route-failure in unstable sensor networks, in this paper, we propose a fully anonymous routing protocol with self-healing capability in unstable sensor networks by constructing a new key agreement scheme and proposing an anonymous identity scheme. The proposed protocol maintains full anonymity of sensor nodes with the self-healing capability of anonymous routes. The results from the performance analysis show that the proposed self-healing anonymity-focused protocol achieves full anonymity of source nodes, destination nodes and communication association.

Keywords: Wireless Sensor Network; Anonymous Routing Protocol; Diffie-Hellman Key Exchange Algorithm; Anonymous Identification Scheme; Self-healing Capability

1. Introduction

With the development of embedded and wireless communication technologies, wireless sensor networks (WSNs) have received increasing attention. Although sensor nodes have limitations of processing volume, battery capacity and other factors, with the advantages of self-organization, dynamical management, reliability and data-centric characteristics, they can be rapidly deployed to surveillance areas, such as battlefields, deserts and so on [1,2]. **Therefore, wireless sensor networks will be continuously deployed and developed.**

However, due to the large-scale deployment of wireless sensor networks on the Internet, they face critical security and privacy issues. Anonymous technology is an effective method to protect the privacy of the network users. It hides the relationship between the two parties through certain methods, and protects the identity privacy of the communicators from being hacked [3,4]. During the communication, network users use the anonymous mechanism of network applications to hide their IP addresses and other personal information, and thus protect identity privacy. Anonymity in sensor networks prevents third parties other than the message sender and the base station from knowing the identity of both parties in the communication [5,6]. It includes source nodes anonymity, communication association anonymity, and destination nodes anonymity. **In 2004, Roger et al. present Tor, a circuit-based low-latency anonymous communication service [7].** In 2018, Mougy et al. used a cryptographic technology and key distribution algorithms to implement the "onion routing" function on the sensor devices, and proposed a privacy protection method for wireless sensor networks based on onion routing [8]. In 2019, Zhou et al. proposed an anonymous routing scheme to protect location

33 privacy in wireless sensor networks by setting a proxy source node and setting a branch area around
34 the base station [9].

35 Self-healing anonymous routing achieves self-healing on the basis of anonymous routing. In
36 many cases, wireless sensor networks are unstable, and their topologies may change over time. In
37 2019, Baranov et al. proposed the self-healing concept in routing protocols. We call a routing algorithm
38 "self-healing" if it satisfies the following two conditions:

- 39 (1) After the local network topology changes, the route can be modified locally and dynamically, and
40 finally the route is optimized and the total energy consumption is saved.
- 41 (2) When the network topology changes, it is not necessary to reinitiate the routing request and route
42 reply, which greatly improves the system efficiency [10].

43 Self-healing can ensure that routes can effectively adapt to the changes of the network topology
44 on the unstable sensor networks. In 2009, Chen et al. proposed a multi-next hop self-healing routing
45 technology based on loop avoidance and local fast self-healing methods e.g. [11]. In 2015, to solve the
46 problems of severe routing flooding and poor self-healing performance of existing wireless network
47 routing algorithms, Zhang et al. proposed a centralized self-healing routing algorithm by introducing
48 the idea of centralized routing and multi-route strategy into self-healing routing [12]. In 2019, Baranov
49 et al. proposed a lightweight decentralized adaptive anonymous routing scheme by combining onion
50 routing for the initial global route request and threshold-based secret sharing for the subsequent local
51 route tuning/healing [10].

52 Most of the existing self-healing anonymous communication protocols in wireless sensor networks
53 cannot provide source node anonymity, destination nodes anonymity and communication association
54 anonymity at the same time. The attacker can track the source node or the base station according
55 to the identity field in the message. If the identity or location of the source node or the destination
56 node is leaking, it may cause large damage to the deployed sensor networks [13]. Therefore, it is very
57 important to maintain the anonymity of nodes during data communication [14].

58 **In order to solve the problem of route-failure and weak anonymity in the existing self-healing**
59 **anonymous routing protocol**, this paper proposes an enhanced anonymous routing protocol with
60 self-healing capability in unstable sensor networks. The key contributions of this paper are listed as
61 follows.

62 (1) A new anonymous identities scheme is proposed. It includes three parts.

- 63 • A novel key distribution and sharing scheme is proposed to provide keys for the following
64 anonymous identity generation and updating process.
- 65 • A new anonymous identity generation scheme is proposed to protect the identity privacy of the
66 sensor nodes.
- 67 • A new anonymous identity updating mechanism is proposed to prevent long-term passive
68 eavesdroppers from inferring network topology through traffic analysis.

69 (2) Based on the former proposed anonymous identities scheme, a fully anonymous routing protocol
70 with self-healing capability is proposed, which can be applied into unstable sensor networks.

71 The paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we present the fundamental knowledge used in
72 this paper. Section 3 reveals the proposed a self-healing enhanced anonymous routing protocol and its
73 performance analysis. Section 4 concludes the whole paper.

74 2. Preliminary

75 2.1. On-demand route discovery

76 In on-demand routing protocols, the route from the source node to the destination node is
77 established only when the source node needs to communicate with the destination node [15].

78 When the network needs to send over data but no available route is found, the source node
79 broadcasts a RREQ (Route REQuest) message to all its neighbors. After the neighbor node has received

80 the RREQ message, it broadcasts the RREQ message to its neighbors until the destination node is
 81 reached. When the RREQ message reaches the destination node, the destination node will answer with
 82 a RREP (Route REPLY) message. When the source node receives the RREP message, it indicates that
 83 the route has been established and it is now ready to communicate.

84 Once the node receives the RREP message, the routing table is created. A routing table entry
 85 is responsible for the routing to reach a destination IP address. The routing table structure is shown
 86 in Table 1. In order to keep the route up-to-date, the routing table needs to maintain the destination
 87 sequence number so that the expired or damaged route can be quickly recovered.

Table 1. Routing Table Structure

The serial number of the destination	The destination IP address	The number of hops required to reach the destination
The symbol of the legitimate destination serial number		
Other status and routing symbol bits		
Network Interface		
Next hop		
Survival time		

88 The maintenance of the neighbor node is mainly implemented by broadcasting the *Hello* message
 89 regularly. When a node is in an active route, it notifies the adjacent node of its own survival by
 90 broadcasting a *Hello* message to the adjacent node. The node first determines whether or not it is
 91 in an active route. If so, it turns on the timer, and it checks every *HELLO_INTERVAL* millisecond
 92 whether *Hello* message or RREQ has been broadcast in the past *HELLO_INTERVAL* millisecond, and
 93 broadcasts a new *Hello* message for the other case. If the system has not received a *Hello* message
 94 from the neighbor, the node considers the neighbor to be invalid and deletes the neighbor from the
 95 contacts [16].

96 When a link fails, all the adjacent nodes that directly use the link produce a RERR message, and
 97 the nodes are then linked to the other nodes. The other nodes will do the same thing until all the
 98 affected nodes receive the RERR(Route ERROR) message. Whether the source node or intermediate
 99 node needs to send data again to the affected destination node after the link failure, it needs to send
 100 RREQ message again to discover the route to the destination node [17,18].

101 2.2. Homomorphic encryption

102 Homomorphic encryption provides a function to process the encrypted data. It can perform
 103 mathematical operations without decrypting the data, which is equivalent to performing operations on
 104 the original data. An encryption scheme is called a homomorphic encryption scheme if it satisfies the
 105 following operations: $E(x) \odot E(y) = E(x \otimes y), \forall x, y \in M$, where E delegates the encryption algorithm
 106 , M delegates the space of all the possible messages, \odot and \otimes delegate two different operations applied
 107 to the plaintext field and to the ciphertext field respectively [19].

108 If " \otimes " delegates an addition operation, the scheme is an addition homomorphism. At the same
 109 time, " \odot " means a multiplication operation.

110 If " \otimes " delegates a multiplication operation, the scheme is a multiplication homomorphism. At
 111 the same time, " \odot " means an addition operation.

112 The Paillier homomorphic encryption scheme is a public key encryption scheme based on
 113 the security assumption of the decisive combinatorial residue class problem. It is an addition
 114 homomorphism [10].

115 Key generation:

116 For large prime numbers p and q with $\gcd(pq, (p-1)(q-1)) = 1$, calculate $n = pq$ and $\omega =$
 117 $\text{lcm}(p-1, q-1)$. Then, a random integer $g \in Z_{n^2}^*$ is selected satisfying $\gcd(n, L(\text{pow}(g, \omega \bmod n^2))) =$

118 1, where the function L is defined for each $u \in Z_{n^2}^*$ as follows: $L(u) = (u - 1)/n$. As a result, the public
119 key is (n, g) and the private key is (p, q) .

120 Encryption:

121 The message x is encrypted as follows.

122 $c = E(x) = g^{xr^n} \pmod{n^2}$, where r is a randomly selected number.

123 Decryption:

124 Ciphertext $c < n^2$ can be decrypted as below:

125 $D(c) = (L(c^\omega \pmod{n^2}) / L(g^\omega \pmod{n^2})) \pmod{n} = x$, using the private key (p, q) .

126 Homomorphic Property:

127 $E(x) * E(y) = (g^{xr_1^n} \pmod{n^2}) * (g^{yr_2^n} \pmod{n^2}) = g^{x+y}(r_1 * r_2)^n \pmod{n^2} = E(x+y)$,
128 whereas r_1 and r_2 are the random numbers chosen to encrypt x and y respectively.

129 In addition to homomorphism over "+", Paillier's encryption scheme has some specific
130 homomorphic properties, which allow extra operations on plaintexts x and y by using the encrypted
131 plaintexts $E(x)$, $E(y)$ and public key pair (n, g) :

$$E(x) * E(y) \pmod{n^2} = E(x+y \pmod{n}), \quad (1)$$

$$E(x) * g^y \pmod{n^2} = E(x+y \pmod{n}), \quad (2)$$

$$E(x)^y \pmod{n^2} = E(x * y \pmod{n}). \quad (3)$$

132 We use Paillier cryptosystem can significantly to reduce the overall computational load on the
133 network: The relay nodes build a cryptographic onion architecture, which can be decoded at the
134 destination in a single pass of asymmetric decryption using its private key. And the lightweight
135 encryption and decryption algorithms are implemented.

136 2.3. Cryptographic system

137 An asymmetric cryptographic system *SysGlobal* with the encryption $E()$, decryption $D()$ and
138 m -bounded homomorphic decomposition properties, is considered. The main operation consists of the
139 proper triple functions $Merge()$, $Sep1()$ and $Sep2()$.

140 Here we introduce a technical notion of bounded homomorphic decomposition. Let m be
141 some integer. An encryption scheme (E, D) has an m -bounded homomorphic decomposition
142 property, if there exists a triplet of functions $Merge()$, $Sep1()$ and $Sep2()$ such that, taking
143 (sk, pk) for a pair of a secret and a public keys, for any $x, y \in M$ s.t. $x < m$
144 and $y < m$ we have: $Sep1(D(Merge(E(x, pk), E(y, pk)), sk)) = D(E(x, pk), sk)$ and
145 $Sep2(D(Merge(E(x, pk), E(y, pk)), sk)) = D(E(y, pk), sk)$.

146 The Paillier Cryptosystem has a m -bounded homomorphic decomposition. In the Paillier
147 Cryptosystem, the functions of $Merge()$, $Sep1()$ and $Sep2()$ are defined as follow.

148 For any $m < \sqrt{n}$:

$$Merge(x, y) = E(x)^m * E(y) \pmod{n^2} = c. \quad (4)$$

$$Sep1(D(c)) = D(c)(div\ m) = x. \quad (5)$$

$$Sep2(D(c)) = D(c) \pmod{m} = y. \quad (6)$$

149 Where $E(x)$ is the encryption of the message x and $E(y)$ is the encryption of the message y . m is
150 an index, c is encrypted ciphertext. When the ciphertext c is decrypted, the original messages can be
151 obtained after the division operation of $Sep1$ and the modulus operation of $Sep2$.

152 The proof is conducted as follows:

153 Taking into account inequalities $x < m$, $y < m$ and $m < \text{sqrt}(n)$.

154 According to the two homomorphic properties of the Pailliar scheme:

$$E(x) * E(y) \pmod{n^2} = E(x + y \pmod{n}). \quad (1)$$

$$E(x)^y \pmod{n^2} = E(x * y \pmod{n}). \quad (3)$$

155 We can have:

$$156 D(c) = D(E(x)^m * E(y)) = D(E(x * m) * E(y)) = D(E(x * m + y)) = x * m + y.$$

157 *SysGlobal* is used in the RREQ process. The asymmetry in the system *SysGlobal* is that the public
158 key of the destination node is used to encrypt the messages and the private key of the destination node
159 is used to decrypt message.

160 The other symmetric cryptographic system *SysLocal* with polynomial time encryption $E_{fast}()$ and
161 polynomial time decryption $D_{fast}()$ is considered.

162 *SysLocal* is used in the RREP process when a reply message is sent from the destination node to
163 the source node. It's a symmetric encryption algorithm. During the RREQ process, each node stores
164 a key locally and sends it to the destination node. Then, the destination node can use the received
165 symmetric keys to encrypt the RREP message layer by layer. At last, during the RREP process, each
166 relay node decrypts a layer with a symmetric key stored locally.

167 3. Fully anonymous routing protocol with self-healing capability

168 In this section, the calculated anonymous identities are used to communicate between sensors.
169 It effectively prevents malicious nodes from identifying the sender and the receiver by reading
170 intercepted messages from the network. A Fully anonymous routing protocol with self-healing
171 capability is proposed by combining the anonymous identity with the lightweight encryption and
172 decryption algorithms. It achieves full anonymity and self-healing capability in sensor networks.

173 In sensor networks, the sensor nodes send the collected data to the base stations. The architecture
174 of the on-demand anonymous routing protocol is presented in Section 3.1. The parameters required
175 for the system are accounted for in Section 3.2. Generation and sharing of anonymous keys, generation
176 and updating of anonymous identities are introduced in Section 3.3. The establishment of on-demand
177 anonymous routes and the self-healing process of anonymous routes are reported in Section 3.4.
178 Performance analysis results are reported in Section 3.5.

179 3.1. Architecture

180 In the wireless sensor networks, sensor nodes need to send the data to the base station. In
181 this situation, these sensor nodes act as source nodes and the base stations act as destination nodes.
182 However, in the wireless sensor networks, the source node S cannot directly communicate with
183 the destination node G , and intermediate nodes are needed to form a multi-hop route to relay the
184 information.

185 This paper presents a routing protocol based on on-demand route discovery. When the source
186 node S advocates a transmitting route to the destination node, it sends the routing request message
187 RREQ to all its neighbors. When an intermediate node receives RREQ, its address is attached to the
188 message, and the information is shared with its neighbors, and so on. When the destination receives
189 the request RREQ, it generates a route reply message RREP. The reply is transmitted to the source node
190 S along the reverse route where all the intermediate nodes have been constructed. The source node
191 S thus obtains a multi-hop route to the destination node G . Then, the node S saves the established
192 route to the routing table. However, as the number of the sessions increases, the routing table is quite
193 large. Node S can first use the timeliness of the routing table entry to record only the most recent route.
194 Its implementation can learn from the LRU algorithm (the Least Recently Used Page Replacement

Figure 1. Architecture of On-demand Anonymous Routing Protocol

Algorithm). The basic idea is to select the record with the longest distance from the current access time and eliminate it. Node *S* set up a record stack, when a record is accessed, immediately push it into the record stack, and check whether or not the same records are just pushed into the top of the stack, if there are, then pull out the original records from the record stack, to ensure that the same records are not stacked. When a record is eliminated by the system, a record elimination is always taken from the bottom of the record stack, that is, the eliminated record is the longest unused.

In Figure 1, the route $S - A - B - G$ is a multi-hop route to the destination node *G* established by the on-demand routing strategy.

3.1.1. Anonymity adversaries

Anonymity means the sender anonymity and the receiver anonymity, used to hide the sender identity and the receiver identity. Only the neighboring nodes in the route 'know' each other. By this way, no matter it is external or internal, no matter it is non-compromised sensors and compromised sensors, any other node cannot identify the source sender and receiver of the message. If a node in the route is compromised by an adversary, it can find its previous hop node, but it cannot find the entire route.

3.1.2. Anonymous compromise

In the paper, anonymous compromise means that the IDs are revealed, or the anonymous route is revealed. As for the question from the reviewer, if $(x_1, y_1)(x_2, y_2)(x_3, y_3)$ constitutes a communication route, the adversary can find out a route with nodes in positions $(x_1, y_1)(x_2, y_2)(x_3, y_3)$, then it is surely a compromised route. The proposed anonymous identities scheme can assure the real IDs and the anonymous routes be hidden.

3.2. System initialization

Each node is preloaded with the public system parameters $(G_0, G_1, G_2, H_1, H_2)$.

In the system initialization phase, we define a public key pre-distribution operation. The public key distribution of all sensor nodes is performed by *CA* (Certificate Authority). In the proposed routing scheme, *CA* is acted by the sink node, that is, *CA* is located in the sink node. All the nodes communicate with the *CA* node to obtain all the public keys of other nodes in the pre-distribution operation. The signature of the *CA* can avoid the man-in-the-middle attack when communicating with the *CA* authentication center.

The symbols used in the proposed full anonymous communication scheme are defined as follows:

Table 2. Symbols definition

symbol	meaning
$Key_{i,N}$	Paired keys shared by node i and neighbor node N
$HIA_{ID,i \leftrightarrow j}$	One-hop anonymous identity shared between node i and node j
$Key_{i \leftrightarrow j}$	The shared key between node i and node j used to update their anonymous identities
$D_{i \rightarrow j}$	Data transferred from node i to node j
H_1, H_2	Hash functions
pk_G	Public key of destination node G
sk_G	Private key of destination node G
R	A random number
S	The source node with address S
G	The destination node with address G
z_{N_i}	A symmetric key of N_i used in RREP process
$SessID$	A unique Session ID used in RREQ and RREP processes
K_{N_i}	The key of N_i used to unlock additional routing packets
ID_i	The real ID of node i
λ	security parameter
$\mathbb{G}_0, \mathbb{G}_1, \mathbb{G}_2$	cyclic group
p	prime order
g	generator

225 3.3. Anonymous identities scheme

226 In this section, a new anonymous identity scheme is proposed through the following three
 227 operations. Firstly, each sensor node is assigned a pair of public and private keys for anonymous key
 228 exchange and sharing. Secondly, an anonymous identity for each hop is calculated by each sending
 229 node. At last, the anonymous identity is updated by each sending node after the data is forwarded.

230 3.3.1. Generation and sharing of anonymous keys

231 In order to calculate the anonymous identities of two nodes when they communicate, the
 232 anonymous keys are introduced.

233 Here, we use the *DH* algorithm to realize the generation and sharing of anonymous $Key_{i,N}$. We
 234 introduce a security parameter λ to make the system more secure. The security parameter λ is used to
 235 generate the system parameters $SP=(\mathbb{G}_0, p, g)$ needed for the anonymous key generation and sharing.
 236 With the increase of security parameters, the length of the key will be increased, and the ability of the
 237 system to resist adversary calculation is greatly enhanced.

238 The system parameter generation algorithm takes as input a security parameter λ . Here, the
 239 security parameter delegates the length of the prime number. We have set λ over 384 bit length
 240 according to the latest *NIST* standard (i.e. 512 bit-length). Then the system parameter generation
 241 algorithm generates security parameters. We let \mathbb{G} denote a generic, polynomial-time, group-generation
 242 algorithm, which takes 1^λ as input and outputs a cyclic group \mathbb{G}_0 , with its prime order p ($|p| = \lambda$),
 243 and one of its generators $g \in \mathbb{G}_0$.

244 It chooses the cyclic group (\mathbb{G}_0, p, g) , and returns the system parameters $SP=(\mathbb{G}_0, p, g)$. In Wireless
 245 Sensor Networks, node N is a neighbor of Node i . First, node i and node N negotiate with the
 246 multiplication group \mathbb{G}_0 of prime order p , where the generator of \mathbb{G}_0 is g .

247 Node i computes a shared symmetric key $Key_{i,N} = (pk_N)^{sk_i}$ by using its own private key sk_i and
 248 node N 's public key pk_N . Node N computes a shared symmetric key $Key_{i,N} = (pk_i)^{sk_N}$ using its own
 249 private key sk_N and node i 's public key pk_i . By this way, node i and node N can obtain their same
 250 shared key.

251 Due to the fact that the *DH* Algorithm itself does not provide any information about the identity
 252 of the two parties, it is vulnerable to the limitations of the man-in-the-middle attack. We introduce an
 253 additional auxiliary tool, the *CA* authentication center in the *PKI* system, to provide authentication to

254 the public key. Digital Certificate provides a simple way to release public key. All participants release
 255 their public key by applying to *CA* for authentication, and verify to *CA* that they have obtained other
 256 party's public key. Then both sides of communication can get each other's public key, and can verify
 257 each other's identity information by digital signature. Recognizing each other's identities by verifying
 258 the *CA* signatures, essentially avoiding active man-in-the-middle attack. After the verification is
 259 successful, the actual data transfer is carried out.

260 In this way, the anonymous keys of node *i* and its neighbor node *N* are generated and shared.

261 3.3.2. Generation of anonymous identities

262 After the anonymous keys between the two nodes are generated and shared, the anonymous
 263 identity is generated by calculating the key Hash function of the two nodes. The specific generation
 264 process of anonymous identity is as follows.

265 The anonymous identity of a sensor node is generated by Hash function H_1 .

$$266 H_1 : \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{G}_1$$

267 When nodes *i* and *j* are the neighbors of each other, both nodes *i* and *j* can compute their
 268 shared $Key_{i,j}$ by using the Diffie-Hellman algorithm proposed in Section 3.3.1. If node *i* expects to
 269 communicate with its neighbor node *j*, and it can have an anonymous identity as follows.

$$HIA_{ID,i \leftrightarrow j} = H_1 (Key_{i,j} \oplus ID_i \oplus ID_j). \quad (7)$$

270 Where, \oplus delegates the XOR operation.

271 That is, the anonymous identity of node *i* is a hashed result from the shared key between nodes *i*
 272 and *j*, the identity of node *i*, and the identity of node *j*.

273 After the anonymous identity is calculated, both nodes *i* and *j* can share the anonymous identity,
 274 which is similar to the "secret signal" agreed by both sides, and realizes the function of identity
 275 authentication. Any third party other than these two parties cannot calculate to obtain this "secret
 276 signal".

277 Nodes *i* and *j* communicate with the shared anonymous identity $HIA_{ID,i \leftrightarrow j}$, which fulfills the
 278 identities authentication between two nodes whilst ensuring that the adversary cannot obtain its real
 279 identity.

280 3.3.3. Update of anonymous identities

281 In order to solve the problem that a long-term passive eavesdropper can infer the real identities
 282 of the users by traffic analysis, the sensor nodes update the anonymous identities after the data is
 283 forwarded. The details are as follows.

284 The anonymous identities of the sensor nodes are updated by hash function H_2 .

$$285 H_2 : \mathbb{G}_2 \times \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \{0, 1\}^n.$$

286 When nodes *i* and *j* are the neighbors of each other, node *i* computes a pair of shared key $Key_{i \leftrightarrow j}$
 287 with node *j* to update anonymous identity $HIA_{ID,i \leftrightarrow j}$,

$$Key_{i \leftrightarrow j} = H_2 (Key_{i,j} \oplus ID_i \oplus ID_j). \quad (8)$$

$$HIA_{ID,i \leftrightarrow j} = H_1 (Key_{i \leftrightarrow j} \oplus HIA_{ID,i \leftrightarrow j}). \quad (9)$$

288 3.4. Fully anonymous routing protocol with self-healing capability

289 The anonymous identities scheme proposed in Section 3.3 is introduced into this section to
 290 implement the fully anonymous routing protocol with self-healing capability.

291 When the source node *S* intends to communicate with the destination node *G*, the source node
 292 *S* broadcasts the RREQ messages to all its neighbors, which act as the intermediate nodes in the
 293 anonymous route. Each intermediate node broadcasts the RREQ message to its own neighbors, and

294 so on, till the broadcasts the RREQ messages reaches the destination node. Assuming that the route $S - A - B - G$ is the first route to the destination node, the messages return along this route.

Figure 2. Route Establishment

295 During the route establishment process, each node creates an anonymous identity to hide its true
 296 identity before sending a message to the next node. After the message has been sent, the sending node
 297 updates the anonymous identity for the following interaction, to avoid the repeated use of the same
 298 anonymous identity.
 299

300 The broadcasting process scheduled by the neighboring nodes is as follows.

301 When broadcasting the RREQ message, the broadcast node first computes its own sharing
 302 anonymous identities. Then it selects a symmetric key from the SysLocal cryptosystem and encrypts
 303 it together its address. At last it constructs and broadcasts the RREQ message (including session ID,
 304 anonymous identity, encrypted symmetric key and address, and the public key of destination node).

305 When its neighbor node receives the corresponding RREQ message, it first authenticates the
 306 validity of the message. If the message is valid, it will perform the following steps.

307 Firstly, it stores the corresponding session ID. Secondly, it selects and saves its symmetric key
 308 with the destination node locally. Thirdly, it encrypts its own address and symmetric key with the
 309 public key of the destination node. Fourthly, it constructs and broadcast the new RREQ message to its
 310 own neighbors.

311 The following nodes execute the same operations until the RREQ message reaches the destination
 312 node.

313 This protocol is divided into two parts, including the establishment of the on-demand anonymous
 314 route and the self-healing of the anonymous route. The anonymous identity sets up for each sensor
 315 node is used in the RREQ request and RREP reply routes, and finally the route self-healing capability
 316 is implemented in the RREP reply route.

317 3.4.1. Establishment of on-demand anonymous routes

318 (1) Anonymous RREQ process.

- 319 • The source node communicates with its neighbor candidate node

320 When source S starts to look for a new route for destination node G , it will work as follows.

321 Step1: Randomly select a new session ID $SessID$ and a new key z_S from the *SysLocal*
 322 cryptosystem, and store it in the local storage in the form of $[SessID, z_S]$.

323 Step2: Node S creates the one-hop anonymous identity $HIA_{ID,S \leftrightarrow N} = H_1 (Key_{S,N} \oplus ID_S \oplus ID_N)$
 324 between node S and the next neighbor node N .

325 Step3: Calculate $Key_{S \leftrightarrow N} = H_2 (Key_{S,N} \oplus ID_S \oplus ID_N)$ and encrypt pk_G with $Key_{S \leftrightarrow N}$.

Step4: The created anonymous identity is used to compose the broadcast RREQ message with the following five attributes:

$$E_{pk_N}(SessID) || HIA_{ID,S \leftrightarrow N} || E_{Key_{S \leftrightarrow N}}(pk_G) || E(S, pk_G) || E(z_S, pk_G)$$

Where the symbol $||$ means the concatenation operation.

Let $\alpha = E(S, pk_G), \mu = E(z_S, pk_G)$, and source node S send the message to the next neighbor node.

Step5: Update $HIA_{ID,S \leftrightarrow N}$.

- The intermediate node communicates with its neighbor candidate node

When an intermediate node with address N receives a message in the form of $E_{pk_N}(SessID) || HIA_{ID,S \leftrightarrow N} || E_{Key_{S \leftrightarrow N}}(pk_G) || \alpha || \mu$, it will work as follows.

Step1: Select a new key z_N randomly from the *SysLocal* cryptosystem, and store it in the local storage in the form of $[SessID, z_N]$;

Step2: Node N creates an anonymous ID, the one-hop anonymous identity $HIA_{ID,N \leftrightarrow N_i}$ between node N and the next neighbor node N_i .

Step3: Decrypt $E_{Key_{S \leftrightarrow N}}(pk_G)$ with $Key_{S \leftrightarrow N}$ to retrieve pk_G , and then use $Key_{N \leftrightarrow N_i}$ to encrypt pk_G .

Step4: Construct the anonymous identity that communicates with the next neighbor node to form the new RREQ message:

$$E_{pk_{N_i}}(SessID) || HIA_{ID,N \leftrightarrow N_i} || E_{Key_{N \leftrightarrow N_i}}(pk_G) || Merge(E(N, pk_G), \alpha) || Merge(E(z_N, pk_G), \mu).$$

Let $\alpha = Merge(E(N, pk_G), \alpha), \mu = Merge(E(z_N, pk_G), \mu)$, and send the message to the next neighbor node.

Step5: Update $HIA_{ID,N \leftrightarrow N_i}$.

- Destination node receives forwarding data

When the destination node G receives the data α , it uses the theorem $Sep(D(Merge(E(x_1, pk), \dots, E(x_l, pk)), sk), i) = D(E(x_i, pk), sk)$ of bounded decomposition to easily recover the whole route $S.N_1.N_2 \dots N_m.G$.

$$N_m := Sep1(D(\alpha, sk_G)); \beta_1 := Sep2(D(\alpha, sk_G));$$

$$N_{m-1} := Sep1(D(\beta_1, sk_G)); \beta_2 := Sep2(D(\beta_1, sk_G));$$

...

$$N_1 := Sep1(D(\beta_{m-1}, sk_G)); \beta_m := Sep2(D(\beta_{m-1}, sk_G));$$

$$S := Sep1(D(\beta_m, sk_G)).$$

Similarly, when the destination node G receives the data μ , it can recover the keys z_S, z_{N_1}, \dots, z_G stored locally at each node of the route. These keys can be used for fast encryption and decryption of any message exchange between the destination node and the corresponding intermediate node (in the context of the current session) during the route reply process.

In the process of route establishment, lightweight encryption can also be used. Paillier homomorphic encryption can carry out mathematical operation on the basis of non-decrypted data, which is equivalent to the operation on the original data [20]. In this case, the system allows the encrypted data to be processed directly without decryption. Using the Paillier homomorphism property, when $Merge(E(N, pk_G), \alpha)$ is calculated, it is directly operated on the basis of the encrypted data, and there is no decryption operation for α . On the other hand, when $Merge(E(z_N, pk_G), \mu)$ is calculated, it is directly operated on the basis of the encrypted data, and there is no decryption operation for μ .

Specifically, we encrypt the address of the source node S and the address of the next hop N of the source node to get the ciphertext c :

362 $Merge(E(N, pk_G), E(S, pk_G)) = E(N, pk_G)^m * E(S, pk_G) \pmod{n^2} = c.$

363 When the destination node receives the ciphertext c , the source node and its next hop address
364 can be obtained by decrypting the ciphertext c using *Sep1* and *Sep2*.

365 The proposed scheme is suitable for wireless sensor networks composed of micro devices with
366 very low processing power, storage and battery power.

367 (2) Anonymous RREP process.

368 In the RREP process, a symmetric cryptosystem *SysLocal* with polynomial time encryption $E_{fast}()$
369 and polynomial time decryption $D_{fast}()$ is considered.

370 When the message arrives at the destination node G , G needs to send a reply message to the
371 source node. In this process, we achieve the full anonymity from the destination node to the source
372 node.

373 In the route reply process, the destination node uses the key z_{N_i} of each node decrypted to encrypt
374 symmetrically. This is done using the idea of ‘‘onion routing’’, first in the destination node sequential
375 encrypts n layer, and then in the process of the reply layer by layer decryption. The first layer is
376 encrypted with the symmetric key of the source node, and the second layer is encrypted with the
377 symmetric key of the adjacent node of the source node, and so on, till the destination node’s neighbor
378 encrypts the n th layer, just like an ‘‘onion’’.

379 Destination node G sends the data with three attributes to adjacent node N_m .

380 $E_{pk_{N_m}}(SessID) || HIA_{ID, G \leftrightarrow N_m} || E_{fast}(K_{N_m} || N_{m-1} || Suffix_{m-1}, z_{N_m})$

381 Suffix is defined as follows:

382 $Suffix_i = E_{fast}(K_{N_i} || N_{i-1} || Suffix_{i-1}, z_{N_i}), i > 1,$

383 $Suffix_1 = E_{fast}(K_{N_1} || S || R, z_{N_1}), R$ is a random number.

384 Where, K_{N_i} is a node specific key (or a group of keys) for unlocking additional special routing
385 packets Pkt in the route self-healing process.

386 After the intermediate node N_m receives the data, it can be decrypted with its local
387 symmetric key z_{N_m} to gain $K_{N_m} || N_{m-1} || Suffix_{m-1}$. The decrypted K_{N_m} is stored locally,
388 then N_m finds the next node of the reply route via N_{m-1} , and sends the decrypted
389 $Suffix_{m-1} = E_{fast}(K_{N_{m-1}} || N_{m-2} || Suffix_{m-2}, z_{N_{m-1}})$ combined with *SessID* and the calculated
390 anonymous identity $HIA_{ID, m \leftrightarrow m-1}$ to the next node N_{m-1} , and so on, till the data reaches the source
391 node S .

392 When the data reaches the source node S , the source node decrypts it to have a K_{N_S} , the address
393 of S and a random real number R , and the process terminates.

394 3.4.2. Anonymous route self-healing process

395 Here, we consider one of the most common topology modifications: in $A - B - C$ route, nodes A
396 and B are visible to each other, and nodes B and C are visible to each other. Suppose we replace the
397 existing route with a new shorter $A - C$ route. However, nodes A and C know nothing about each
398 other. When nodes A and C can interact directly, we call this self-healing process. [21]

399 The proposed demand route discovery scheme can find an accessible route when it is needed.
400 Honestly, the self-healing is optimization in the normal environment. While in the circumstance where
401 some nodes are unreachable, the optimization becomes a self-healing process. The destination node
402 gets the shortcut information through RREQ messages derived from other nodes. If the destination
403 node gets the shortcut before the anonymous route is built, it will certainly construct and send the
404 refreshed RREP message back through the shorter route.

405 The route self-healing process is implemented in the route reply process, where a special routing
406 packet Pkt is added. This routing package contains some route optimization information shared by the
407 destination node. Initially, a specific packet Pkt is encrypted into $E_{K_{N_i}}(Pkt)$, and the key (the element
408 of K_{N_i}) used to decrypt the special routing packet is distributed by the destination node.

409 In addition, each $E_{K_{N_i}}(Pkt)$ is encrypted by a corresponding symmetric key on the destination
 410 node. For example, if the packet is to be used at the node C , the reply message will contain the
 411 $E_{fast}(E_{K_{N_i}}(Pkt), z_C)$ data block. Therefore, only the node C will be able to decrypt it and we have
 412 $E_{K_{N_i}}(Pkt)$.

Figure 3. Packet Structure of Encryption Route Information

413 If there's a self-healing route, the information in RREP message will include a special routing
 414 packet, which includes the encrypted node IP addresses in the shortcut. That is, when the network
 415 topology changes, if there is a shortcut route $A - C$ between node A and node C , the IP address of the
 416 node A will be put in the special packet, so that the node C can decrypt the IP address of the node A .

417 Specifically, when the destination node finds the shortcut of the route $A - C$, the destination node
 418 puts the information of node A (the IP address of the node A) in an additional special routing package
 419 Pkt , encrypts the routing package into $E_{K_A}(Pkt)$, and only the corresponding K_A can decrypt it. The
 420 $E_{K_A}(Pkt)$ is encrypted by the symmetric key z_C of the corresponding node C at the destination node.

421 When the $E_{fast}(E_{K_A}(Pkt), z_C)$ data block arrives at the node C along the route, z_C decrypts
 422 $E_{K_A}(Pkt)$. When the network topology changes, (1)node A enters the wireless detection area of node
 423 C , (2)node A is connected with node C , (3) K_A can decrypt Pkt , (4)use optimization information in Pkt
 424 (the IP address of the node A) to optimize, and (5) node C can skip B to send frame directly to A . This
 425 completes a route self-healing process.

426 Now some intermediate relay nodes have some routing packets with the hidden routing
 427 information. Each routing packet is encrypted with K_{N_i} . To open it, the node must collect the
 428 required key. This can only be achieved through direct communication between the nodes.

429 3.4.3. Specific implementation process

430 For clarity, a detailed procedure is presented by certain examples. According to the previous
 431 assumption, the route $S - A - B - G$ is the first arrival route, and a concrete implementation process
 432 is given. In the process of route establishment, we encrypt data one by one, and finally decrypt it at
 433 the destination node. In this section, we implement the full anonymity of the entire route from the
 434 source to the destination nodes. The process is as follows:

435 Assuming the route is established as $S \rightarrow A \rightarrow B \rightarrow G$.

436 (1) Anonymous route request message (RREQ) request process

437 Step1: Each node enters a session key z_{N_i} in the encrypted part of its RREQ message to establish a
 438 symmetric encrypted connection with the destination node.

439 Step2: Each sending node constructs an anonymous identity before each forwarding operation,
 440 which prevents the third party other than the sender and receiver from observing the communication
 441 between the two nodes.

Figure 4. RREQ Process

442 Step3: Encrypts the node location information at each new relay node, which prevents the
 443 receiving candidate node from viewing the route that data forwarding has been circulated from the
 444 sender routing.

445 Step4: Each sending node updates its own anonymous identity after the data has been sent, which
 446 prevents long-term passive eavesdroppers extrapolating the network topology through traffic analysis.

447 Conversely, the reply of the base station node (RREP message) is an "onion" and these layers can
 448 be "removed" only by using the symmetric password of the corresponding relay node.

449 (2) Anonymous route reply message (RREP) reply process

450 Based on the previous assumption that the route $S - A - B - G$ is the first arrival route, the RREP
 451 reply process is $G \rightarrow B \rightarrow A \rightarrow S$. The details are as follows:

Figure 5. RREP Process

452 Step1: Node G computes $E_{pk_B}(SessID)||HIA_{ID,G\leftrightarrow B}||E_{fast}(K_B||A||Suffix_A, z_B)$, where
 453 $Suffix_A = E_{fast}(K_A||S||Suffix_S, z_A)$.
 454 Then node G sends $E_{pk_B}(SessID)||HIA_{ID,G\leftrightarrow B}||E_{fast}(K_B||A||Suffix_A, z_B)$ to node B.
 455 At last, node G updates $HIA_{ID,G\leftrightarrow B}$.
 456 Step2: node B decrypts $E_{fast}(K_B||A||Suffix_A, z_B)$ with z_B , gets K_B , the address of A node and
 457 $Suffix_A$.
 458 Then node B sends data $E_{pk_A}(SessID)||HIA_{ID,B\leftrightarrow A}||E_{fast}(K_A||S||Suffix_S, z_A)$ to node A.
 459 At last, node B updates $HIA_{ID,B\leftrightarrow A}$.
 460 Step3: node A decrypts $E_{fast}(K_A||S||Suffix_S, z_A)$ with z_A , gets K_A , the address of the S node and
 461 $Suffix_S$.
 462 Then node A sends data $E_{pk_S}(SessID)||HIA_{ID,A\leftrightarrow S}||E_{fast}(K_S||S||R, z_S)$ to S.
 463 At last, node A update $HIA_{ID,A\leftrightarrow S}$.
 464 Step4: node S decrypts $E_{fast}(K_S||S||R, z_S)$ with z_S , gets its own address and a random number R.
 465 The RREP process terminates.
 466 (3) Anonymous route self-healing process
 467 As an example, the route reply process is $G \rightarrow B \rightarrow A \rightarrow S$, and the destination node has found a
 468 shortcut from node B to node S.

Figure 6. Self-healing Process of Anonymous Routes

469 Step1: The destination node dispatches a key K_{N_i} for each node on the route.
 470 Step2: The destination node places the S node's information in an additional special routing
 471 packet called Pkt and encrypts it to $E_{K_S}(Pkt)$, which can only be decrypted by K_S (where K_S can be the
 472 S node's ID).
 473 Step3: $E_{K_S}(Pkt)$ is encrypted with the symmetric key z_B of node B, which forms a data block
 474 $E_{fast}(E_{K_S}(Pkt), z_B)$.
 475 Step4: The data block goes one step to B along the route, which is $G \rightarrow B \rightarrow A \rightarrow S$, and is
 476 decrypted by B with z_B to obtain $E_{K_S}(Pkt)$.
 477 Step5: If the network topology changes, there is a shortcut from B to S. Now node S is connected
 478 to node B, and then B decrypts $E_{K_S}(Pkt)$ with K_S .
 479 Step6: Using the optimization information in the Pkt , node B skips node A and directly interacts
 480 with the node S.

481 3.5. Performance analysis

482 3.5.1. Anonymity

483 The proposed protocol realizes three kinds of anonymity: source nodes, destination nodes and
 484 communication association anonymity. In this section, we will analyze the anonymity performance of
 485 the proposed protocol under active attacks. It is assumed that the active attackers can compromise
 486 some nodes of a given network and thus extract data from these nodes. However, an attacker cannot
 487 discover the communication association between the base station, source node, and other nodes in a
 488 given network. The detailed analysis is as follows.

489 (1) Source nodes anonymity

490 It is assumed that the active attacker can crack some nodes of a given network and expose data.
 491 However, the attacker can not find the source node. We show the following:

Suppose the source node S passes the underlying data to node N ,

$$E_{pk_N}(SessID) || HIA_{ID,S \leftrightarrow N} || E_{Key_{S \leftrightarrow N}}(pk_G) || E(S, pk_G) || E(z_S, pk_G).$$

492 This transport hides the source node ID and the address information in $HIA_{ID,S \leftrightarrow N}$ and $E(S, pk_G)$.
 493 Assuming this transmission does not encounter a damaged node before reaching the base station, the
 494 attacker can not find the information of the source node based on the intercepted information.

495 (2) Communications association anonymity

496 When the node i communicates with the node j , the shared key of nodes i and j cannot be obtained
 497 for the third party node. Therefore, it is not possible to calculate $HIA_{ID,i \leftrightarrow j} = H_1(Key_{i,j} \oplus ID_i \oplus ID_j)$,
 498 the attack node cannot impersonate the node to communicate, and can not know which two nodes to
 499 communicate, which ensures the anonymity of the communication association.

500 (3) Destination nodes anonymity

501 During data transmission, the packet does not contain any information about the base station.
 502 For passive attackers, it is difficult to find base station nodes from the captured packets. Moreover, the
 503 active attacker can not find the communication association between two nodes as described above, so
 504 it is difficult to find the base station even the active attacker.

505 In Table 3, we give detailed analysis of anonymity in the proposed protocol and the existing
 506 protocols. We infer from Table 3 that *APR* only implements communication association anonymity,
 507 *RandomWalk* only implements destination nodes anonymity [21,22]. However, our proposed protocol
FarpScusn, has achieved all the three types of anonymity simultaneously.

Table 3. Performance Analysis

protocol	Source anonymity	nodes	Communications association anonymity	Destination anonymity	nodes	self-healing
<i>FarpScusn</i>	✓		✓	✓		✓
<i>APR</i>	×		✓	×		×
<i>RandomWalk</i>	×		×	✓		×

508 The improved scheme accomplishes that the adversary cannot determine the identity of the
 509 sender and receiver by extracting the messages intercepted from the network or by extracting the
 510 messages forwarded by its leaking sensor node. The adversary cannot determine whether or not two
 511 communication segments (message transmission between two adjacent nodes) belong to the same
 512 communication between the source and the destination nodes[23].

514 3.5.2. Self-healing capability

515 At present, most anonymous routing protocols do not achieve self-healing capability [24].
 516 Traditional anonymous routing methods need to restart new routing requests and route messages

517 recovery when the network topology changes. The proposed protocol implements local self-healing
 518 capability by adding a small optimized routing package to the route request message while the network
 519 topology changes. And only minimum necessary information on the network topology is provided to
 520 the intermediate nodes.

521 The self-healing capability analysis can be found in Table 3.

522 3.5.3. Security

523 (1) Man-in-the-middle attack

524 We introduce the $SP=(\mathbb{G}_0, p, g)$ generated by the system security parameters λ , and the SP is
 525 secretly negotiated between the nodes and their neighbors. If the adversary wants to modify or delete
 526 the communication information successfully, it must obtain SP .

527 What's more, we introduce an additional auxiliary tool, the CA authentication center in the PKI
 528 system, to provide authentication to the public key. Digital Certificate provides a simple way to release
 529 public key. All participants release their public keys by applying to CA for authentication, and verify
 530 to CA that they have obtained other parties' public keys. Then both sides of communication can get
 531 each other's public keys, and can verify each other's identity information by digital signatures.

532 (2) Mutual authentication

533 When the node i communicates with the node j , the anonymous identity $HIA_{ID,i \leftrightarrow j}$ can be
 534 calculated by both the parties. If equal, the certification is successful.

535 (3) Impersonation attack

536 An adversary intercepts some communication contents through channel and pretends to be a
 537 legitimate user. First, the adversary does not know which two users are communicating. Second, the
 538 adversary cannot calculate the anonymous identity, authenticate, and impersonate.

539 (4) Forward security and backward security

540 The full communication route cannot be obtained by any node except the destination node.

541 3.5.4. Simulation

542 (1) Anonymous Simulation

543 In this section, the position of the real sensor node detected by the adversary is simulated with
 544 *Matlab*, and the result shows that the proposed protocol can effectively protect the anonymity of the
 545 sensor nodes in the communication.

546 In the simulation, we deploy 25 sensor nodes in an area of $1m \times 1m$, where the positions of the
 547 four adversaries are deployed at coordinates $(0,0), (0,1), (1,0), (1,1)$, and blind devices (normal sensors
 548 that need to guess their positions) are deployed in a square surrounded by the adversaries. We
 549 randomly generate a network topology graph from source node S to destination node G and generate
 550 an anonymous route from S to G ($S - A - B - G$), as shown in figure 7.

551 We consider sensor location estimation when sensors measure *Received Signal Strength (RSS)* or
 552 *Time - Of - Arrival (TOA)* between themselves and neighboring sensors. According to the measured
 553 RSS or TOA , the adversaries can estimate the positions of sensor nodes by using the *Maximum*
 554 *Likelihood Estimation (MLE)*. The result is that the adversary can accurately guess the actual positions
 555 of all the blind devices [25,26], as shown in figure 8.

Figure 7. Location of sensors and adversaries and a randomly generated network topology

Figure 8. Real Position of Sensor Detected by Adversary

556 If real identities are used to communicate between the sensor nodes, the adversaries may obtain
 557 the identities of the sensor nodes by intercepting the routing information, and the adversary can
 558 decode the route accurately according to the identities of the sensor nodes, and finally find the actual
 559 location of the communications sensor. For example, if the adversaries intercept the communication
 560 route $S - A - B - G$, they can successfully acquire the entire route, which is shown in figure 9.

Figure 9. The route detected by adversaries after intercepting the sensor's true identity

561 However, the proposed protocol in this paper, using anonymous identities to communicate, and
 562 the adversary cannot intercept the real identities of the sensor nodes, effectively solve the problem,
 563 ensures the anonymity of sensor node communication, as shown in figure 10.

Figure 10. The Adversities cannot obtain the route

564 (2) Self-healing simulation

565 Under normal circumstances, as shown in the figure below, a node in the S-A-B-G route has an
 566 error. If the error occurs at node B, then node S needs to restart the RREQ request to establish a new
 567 route in order to reach node G. This leads to complex process for re-connection, as shown in figure 11
 568 and figure 12.

Figure 11. The error occurs the node B

Figure 12. Simulation without self-healing capability

569 On-demand routing can find an accessible route. The destination node determines the updated
 570 topology based on the received message, and performs route self-healing and optimization. We discuss
 571 this in three ways.

572 Case 1: According to discussion of Section 3.4.2, when the network topology changes, node A
 573 enters the wireless signal area of node C. There is an $A - C$ shortcut in the route $A - B - C$, and node
 574 C can skip B to send the data directly to A. When all the nodes are working properly, if the network
 575 topology changes, and a shortcut between A and G is detected by the destination
 576 node will immediately carry out the following self-healing process, as shown in figure 13.

Figure 13. Simulation of self-healing capability with shortcut

577 Case 2: If there's a shortcut between node *A* and node *G*, when node *B* goes wrong, the destination
 578 node will find the *A* – *G* shortcut, and the self-healing process will be triggered as in the Case 1 and
 579 see Figure 13.

580 Case 3: Assuming that there is no shortcut between node *A* and node *G*, when node *B* has an
 581 error, the destination node will find another accessible route from node *A* to node *G* from other RREQ
 582 messages. The new accessible route will use node *E* in (0.25,0.5) to bypass the error node *B* in the given
 583 example, as shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Simulation of self-healing capability without shortcut

584 4. Conclusion

585 A fully anonymous routing protocol with the self-healing capability in unstable sensor networks
 586 has been proposed in this paper. In the proposed protocol, the Paillier cryptosystem was introduced

587 into the secure anonymous communication scheme to establish an anonymous identity for every
588 sensor node in the network, which realized full anonymity in unstable wireless environments. Each
589 sensor node communicates with its neighbor nodes using the anonymous identity. Each node encrypts
590 its address information with the public key of the destination node, and sends it to the next node in
591 the anonymous route. After the routing packet has arrived at the destination node, the destination
592 node decrypts the entire route with its corresponding private key. Security analysis shows that the
593 proposed protocol realizes source node, destination node and communication association anonymity.
594 This proposed protocol is suitable for protecting the anonymity of sensor nodes and can prevent the
595 adversary from finding the actual nodes such as source node or base station by analyzing the network
596 traffic. The protocol uses a special lightweight implementation tool for wireless sensor networks with
597 low processing power, storage space, and battery power. In the future, we will continue to study on
598 lower energy consumption and safer routing strategies.

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